

Rolling a cosmological dice - randomness in Cosmological Images

Dron Paul Choudhury

dron.pc05@gmail.com

DPS International Saket, New Delhi, Delhi, India

Nishchal Dwivedi

Department of Basic Science and Humanities, SVKM's NMIMS Mukesh Patel School of Technology Management & Engineering, Mumbai, India

Abstract

The origin of universe is studied widely using astronomical data collections not limited to radio astronomy, space telescopes and terrestrial telescopes. In this work we use this collected astrophysical data and look at the possibility of randomness in this data. We find that picking the intensity of any point in such a cosmological image gives a uniform distribution, hinting the inherent uniform randomness of cosmological signals.

Introduction

The origin of the universe has always been one of the fundamental questions that humanity has tried to answer. Based on research in the 20th century, the current model that most suits our understanding of the universe is that of the Big Bang[1]. The ground-breaking discovery of Edwin Hubble in 1929[2] that galaxies were moving away from us paved the way for further studies into the expanding universe. The model of the exponential expansion of the universe was provided by physicist Alan Guth in the 1980s, although the term 'Big Bang' itself was coined by astronomer Fred Hoyle[3].

The universe began from a dense, hot point, where matter was infinitely compressed into a point, a singularity for the ease of understanding. As the universe expanded, it cooled, allowing for the creation of the fundamental particles, from hadrons and lepton, soon to the first atoms from hydrogen and helium nuclei. Overtime, these particles started combining together under gravitational effects to form larger masses of matter, from stars, galaxies and black holes. The interaction between matter and dark matter and the subsequent gravitation effects between them is what forms the fabric of this universe.

Research into the early universe would not have been possible without an understanding of doppler redshift[4]. As the universe expands, so do many galaxies. As light from these galaxies, the source, travels towards us and the space over which they travel stretches, so does the wavelength of these electromagnetic waves. Once these waves reach our planet, their wavelengths have been redshifted. Studies into these redshifted electromagnetic waves are consistent with the theory of the Big Bang.

The best evidence of the Big Bang, however, is provided in the study of Cosmological Microwave Background Radiation (CMB)[5]. Discovered by accident in the 1960s, CMB is a faint spread of

microwave radiation spread across the universe. The first detailed measurements of CMB were made by The Cosmic Background Explorer Telescope (COBE)[6] when it was launched in 1989. Emitted merely 380,000 years after the formation of the universe, CMB is often referred to as the afterglow of the Big Bang. CMB's features proved to be of great importance to this project. CMB exhibits a nearly perfect blackbody spectrum, with an incredibly accurate temperature measurement at 2.7 kelvin. CMB also happens to be isotropic, meaning that it appears to be the same in all directions, following the cosmological principle that the universe, at a sufficiently large scale, appears to be the same in all directions. The most important aspect of the CMB is that it has tiny temperature variations. Despite its overall isotropic nature, CMB does have anisotropies, which represent regions of the universe with varying densities.

Due to presence of multiple sources of light and radiation, advanced cosmological imaging becomes a very important tool to study the knowledge of the known universe. In this work, we use images obtained from astrophysical sources to study this randomness.

A random number, as the name suggests occurs without any predictable pattern or order[7]. It is generated without any relationship to the past random numbers. The occurrence of a random number can only be predicted by a probability, but can never be fully determined unless it has already been generated. A random number has three fundamental properties. They are unpredictable, independent of each other and occur based on a uniform distribution.

A random number generator has a multitude of uses[8]. Broadly, its uses can be classified into four branches. The first branch is cryptography and security. These include cryptographic keys for encryption algorithms, and token and unique identifiers for authentication systems. The second branch is that of scientific research and simulations. Random number generators are used to model weather patterns, economic models, the growth of crops etc. The third branch is sampling and surveys, where these generators are used to simulate survey results on a variety of variables. The last and final branch is software development and other high tech development programs. This, thus, establishes the importance of the random number generators.

Aim

The aim of this paper is to study the statistical distribution of randomly picking a point in the universe and looking at the intensities. We explore if such a source of data can be used to create a simple pseudo-random number generator. The broader aim of this research paper was to examine potential alternate sources of random numbers in the future, in order to mitigate algorithmic tendencies that may reduce the randomness quotient of the output.

Literature Review

In order to conduct this research, a literature review was conducted based on the work that has already been done in the creation of random number generators using cosmological data. This research paper takes inspiration from many such works. The summary of some of the important works are given below, based on which this research was conducted:

1. MRNG: Accessing Cosmic Radiation as an Entropy Source for a Non-Deterministic Random Number Generator[9]

This paper presents a novel method for using Ultra High Energy Cosmic Rays (UHECR)[10] captured by an image sensor in common smartphones as a cheap, robust, and readily available source of true randomness. The authors propose an algorithm that can extract randomness from UHECR and cosmic radiation on a smartphone to be embedded it into a Random Number Generator (RNG). Although slow, RNG provides a strong and cost-effective randomness suitable for any system in need of locally generated true random numbers. The prototype builds on the existing Cosmic Ray Extremely Distributed Observatory (CREDO)[11] Android application, which collects images of UHECR and muons. The researchers show that random numbers can be extracted from UHECR, describe four methods that, in combination, extract randomness out of UHECR, and prove that the extracted random sequence is truly random when tested against a statistical test suite.

2. Celestial Sources for Random Number Generation [12]

This paper presents an alternative method for gathering seed data for random number generation (RNG) in cryptographic applications. The method uses the inherent randomness of signal data from celestial sources in radio astronomy to provide seeds for RNG. Data sets were collected from two separate celestial sources and run through an algorithm to produce uniform random numbers. The resulting data sets pass all tests in the NIST Statistical Test Suite [13] for random data, with a mean of 98.9% of the 512 total bitstreams from the two sources passing all tests in the NIST suite and further testing in R. These results are on par with the control set generated using Java's SecureRandom function[14]. The data sets tested all offered high performance levels in statistical tests for randomness over long period bitstreams, suggesting that astronomical data retrieved from celestial sources presents a viable option for implementing secure systems and cryptographic functions such as SHA-256. Further research is necessary to determine the most effective use of this type of astronomical data in cryptographic applications, including examination of other sources, comparison of data from other radio telescopes, and testing the astronomical data with multiple different RNGs for performance.

Given that the aim of this project was to merge two distinct fields to create a random number generator, I also drew from other similar works that used two distinct fields.

3. Quantum Random Number Generators[15]

Quantum random number generators (QRNGs)[16] are devices that use quantum mechanical effects to produce random numbers, with applications ranging from simulation to cryptography. These devices are simpler than other quantum devices and have gone from the lab to the shelves with at least eight existing commercial products. In recent years, there have been numerous proposals, experiments, improvements, and theoretical results in randomness extraction and randomness certification. This review aims to collect the most important proposals for quantum random number generation and introduce new advanced protocols that use quantum physics to process, certify, or deal with random strings.

The paper covers the most important applications of randomness in science and computers, focusing on applications to simulation and cryptography. It also discusses the main functional elements of quantum random number generators and their roles, as well as mathematical measures of randomness that are useful for analysing the amount of available random bits and the security of quantum random number generators.

The paper also discusses QRNGs based on radioactive decay, electronic noise, and quantum optics, as well as alternative QRNGs based on nonoptical quantum phenomena. It also reviews classical randomness extraction methods and introduces quantum protocols for randomness expansion and amplification that allow for good-quality random outputs from weak randomness sources.

Methodology

The data collection procedure involves the usage of openly available data sources. The data was collected from the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes[17], with the data coming from The Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS)[18]. The data was collected in the form of fits files. Python, with PyCharm as its Integrated Development Environment, was used to process the data[19].

A cosmological data in the fits file is an array of arrays which complete as a matrix to build a complete image of a portion of a space. We show an example using a TESS fits file. A single row of array shows the spectrum as shown in figure 1. When many such spectra are collected together, they give a complete image as in figure 2. We used python to plot this spectrum as an image. We further randomly chose a point in the x-y coordinate system and read the spectrum signal strength of the location. This number now serves as a random number for our generator.

A large data output of 2500 integer random numbers were used to construct a histogram to study the distribution of random numbers generated by the algorithm. The figure helps to evaluate the effectiveness of the random number generator.

Results & Discussion

Figure 1. A plot of Signal Strength against position for sample TESS Data

Figure 2. When multiple power spectra are combined as a heat plot, it generates an image for the observed universe.

Figure 3. A histogram to representing the distribution of random numbers generated from a sample output of 2500 generated random numbers. The data shows almost uniform distribution.

It is remarkable to note that on a broad level, the frequency of occurrence appears to be even across the range of numbers hinting to uniform distribution.

The above results show the functional operation of the random number generator. The inherent stochasticity in cosmic data enhances the unpredictability of these numbers[20], consequently improving the security of possible applications in the cryptographic keys and the accuracy of simulations - the main applications of pseudo-random numbers.

Conclusion

The paper aimed to create a simple pseudo-random number generator using cosmological data. It used cosmological data from the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite. Using PyCharm, Python, the data was processed to create an image and its anisotropies and a plot of signal strength. Using the dimensions of the image, a PyCharm built in random number generation algorithm was used in addition to a 'for loop' to result in the output of a fixed number of integer random numbers. The project was successful in establishing the use case application for cosmological data as a random

number generator which is relevant in fields like the security of cryptographic keys, scientific simulations and models, and software development, to name a few.

In future works, data from other sources of astrophysical importance is being explored.

Limitations

We are always in a quest to come across an example of a true random occurrence in nature. Present random number generators do have to use concepts of pseudo-randomness since their computational systems generate random numbers based on inputted algorithms which means that the numbers aren't truly random in nature. Other problems include limits of observation and measurement inaccuracies that affect the randomness of the values.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank my various research mentors who helped me understand the process of collating information, performing the necessary research and study, and writing this research paper. I would also like to thank my teachers and mentors both in and outside the school - Mr. Saroj Kumar, Ms. Mamta Goyal, and Ms. Shreya Kabir, who helped me arrive at a topic of research, and proofreading my paper to enable me to produce my best possible draft.

References

1. Howell, E., & May, A. (2023, July 26). *What is the Big Bang Theory?* Space.com. <https://www.space.com/25126-big-bang-theory.html>
2. *Edwin Hubble - NASA Science*. (n.d.-b). <https://science.nasa.gov/people/edwin-hubble/>
3. *Formation and Evolution of the Universe | AMNH*. (n.d.). American Museum of Natural History. <https://www.amnh.org/exhibitions/permanent/the-universe/the-universe/formation-and-evolution-of-the-universe#:~:text=Our%20universe%20began%20with%20an,stars%20and%20the%20first%20galaxies.>
4. *Redshift*. (n.d.). <https://lco.global/spacebook/light/redshift/>
5. *Cosmic Microwave Background | Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian*. (2023, September 26). <https://www.cfa.harvard.edu/research/topic/cosmic-microwave-background>
6. *COBE - NASA Science*. (n.d.). <https://science.nasa.gov/mission/cobe/>

7. Wolfram Research, Inc. (n.d.). *Random Number -- from Wolfram MathWorld*.
<https://mathworld.wolfram.com/RandomNumber.html>
8. *How does a Random Number Generator work?* | *Encyclopedia*. (n.d.).
<https://www.hypr.com/security-encyclopedia/random-number-generator>
9. Kutschera, S., Slany, W., Ratschiller, P., Gursch, S., & Dagenborg, H. (2023). MRNG: Accessing Cosmic Radiation as an entropy Source for a Non-Deterministic Random Number Generator. *Entropy*, 25(6), 854. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e25060854>
10. *Cosmic map of Ultrahigh-Energy particles points to Long-Hidden treasures* | *Quanta Magazine*. (2021, May 13). Quanta Magazine. <https://www.quantamagazine.org/cosmic-map-of-ultrahigh-energy-particles-points-to-long-hidden-treasures-20210427/>
11. Homola, P., Beznosko, D., Bhatta, G., Bibrzycki, Ł., Borczyńska, M., Bratek, Ł., Буднев, H. M., Burakowski, D., Alvarez-Castillo, D., Cheminant, K. A., Ćwikła, A., Dam-O, P., Dhital, N., Duffy, A. R., Głownia, P., Gorzkiewicz, K., Góra, D., Gupta, A. C., Hlávková, Z., . . . Woźniak, K. W. (2020). Cosmic-Ray extremely distributed observatory. *Symmetry*, 12(11), 1835. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym12111835>
12. Chapman, E. (n.d.). *Celestial sources for random number generation*. Research Online. <https://ro.ecu.edu.au/ism/190/>
13. Computer Security Division, Information Technology Laboratory, National Institute of Standards and Technology, U.S. Department of Commerce. (n.d.). *NIST SP 800-22: Documentation and Software - Random Bit Generation* | CSRC | CSRC. <https://csrc.nist.gov/projects/random-bit-generation/documentation-and-software>
14. Baeldung, & Baeldung. (2024, January 8). *The Java SecureRandom Class* | Baeldung. Baeldung. <https://www.baeldung.com/java-secure-random>
15. Herrero-Collantes, M., & García-Escartín, J. C. (2017). Quantum random number generators. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 89(1). <https://doi.org/10.1103/revmodphys.89.015004>

16. Alcaide, M. (2023, November 1). *Quantum Random Number Generator (QRNG) - explained*. Quside. <https://quside.com/quantum-random-number-generators-why-how-where/>
17. *MAST Home*. (n.d.). MAST. <https://archive.stsci.edu/>
18. Guerrero, N. (2023, April 20). *TESS - Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite*. TESS. <https://tess.mit.edu/>
19. *PyCharm: the Python IDE for Professional Developers by JetBrains*. (2021, June 2). JetBrains. <https://www.jetbrains.com/pycharm/>
20. Ballardini, M., Finelli, F., & Paoletti, D. (2015). CMB anisotropies generated by a stochastic background of primordial magnetic fields with non-zero helicity. *Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics*, 2015(10), 031. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1475-7516/2015/10/031>